

ISSUES OF HUMAN PERFECTION AND SPIRITUAL DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY IN ALISHER NAVOI AND SHAKESPEARE'S WORK

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Annotation: in this article, Alisher Navoi is a genius writer of the Eastern Renaissance, William Shakespeare is a major representative of the Western Renaissance, and since these two incomparable artists have raised the issues of human perfection and spiritual development of society in their works, they are mentioned side by side, both in terms of proximity to the subject.

Keywords: Western Renaissance, Renaissance, scientific and artistic work, national and international traditions, literary-aesthetic principles, creative style, comparison.

Alisher Navoi is a great person who forms a period in the history of consciousness and thought, artistic culture of our people, an immortal word artist who glorifies the world in honor of the pride and honor of our nation. It is important to compare the creativity of such a poet in the context of national and international traditions with the scientific-theoretical significance. After all, by analogy, the individuality of the poet's creativity, his role in national and world literature is determined.

To date, a number of scientific and artistic works of Alisher Navoi have been translated into foreign languages, hundreds of scientific researches have been carried out on this world-wide heritage. But still the creative style of the great poet, his literary-aesthetic principles, his artistic skills were not studied by analogy with the creativity of Western poet writers who lived and worked in such a period of awakening as he himself.

There are many cases of glorification of Navoi among the major manifestations of Western literature, but one work has not been scientifically investigated so far in

comparison with their particular work. After all, the need to carry out the work in this direction is also a topical issue in the modern comparative literature.

Alisher Navoi is a genius writer of the Eastern Renaissance, and William Shakespeare is a major representative of the Western Renaissance, and since these two incomparable artists have raised the issues of human perfection and spiritual development of society in their works, we have aimed at comparative study of their two works, which are mentioned side by side, both in terms of proximity. We considered that the works of "Leyli and Majnun" and "Romeo and Juliet" will be purposeful if the poets are studied from the point of view of the features of their creative styles. The fact that such comparative work has not yet been carried out in Uzbek literary science, the topic "Navoi and world literature" is a relatively new field in our literary science, and work has been carried out prior to today", and today the need for research in this method determines the relevance of the topic. Navoi and Shakespeare genius-a unique pearl of the world of poetry, the world of miracles inside the miracle.

Alisher Navoi made revolutionary changes in the world of Eastern art and Shakespeare in the world of Western literature. One in Turkish and the other in English raised the prestige of artistic literature to a high level. The generation of mankind is legally proud of these two children of the world. A comparative study of the artistic aspects of the work of Alisher Navoi (1441-1501) and William Shakespeare (1564-1616) may seem to be a very difficult issue for many literary lovers.

The research in the field of scattering the edges of the artistic skills of the creativity of both these poets is not yet noticeable in literary studies. However, such important-tasks as revealing the typological identities in the Western "literary - cultural" relations with their whole integrity are still ahead of us." From this point of view, below we try to show the importance of typological similarities in the literary heritage of Navoi and Shakespeare.

On the basis of our typological analysis it is possible to show the similarity of Navoi and Shakespeare personality, genius, historical and cultural conditions in which they lived and worked. It is known that Navoi's personality and genius are closely related to Herot.

If in the I - half of the XV century Herat rose to the level of the cultural center of Khorasan, then in the second half “that period becomes one of the main centers of the East”

1. Science, especially literature, art, calligraphy, craftsmanship and architecture are widely reported. According to the reports given in the sources, Herotus was the land of the most highly skilled masters, architects, artisans, musicians, in general, various talented great personalities whose names were still mentioned.

2. Bobur says that " ... he is not a bit poet in the mask”

3. In Herat, the role of Navoi in the promotion of prosperity and cultural development to this level was great.

Herat became the center of creativity, created brochures, theses, historical works about art literature, lyrics, morality, calligraphy, painting, music. Development and prosperity can be seen not only in literature and art, but also in all spheres of culture and economy.

This is clearly stated in the works of historians such as Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi, Ibn Arabshah, Mirkhond, Khondamir. Babur writes about the general activity and rise in Khorasan during the International era of Temurids Sultan Hussein in his book. In Conclusion

Alisher Navoi made revolutionary changes in the world of Eastern art and Shakespeare in the world of Western literature. One in Turkish and the other in English raised the prestige of artistic literature to a high level. The generation of mankind is legally proud of these two children of the world.

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